

Role of Motivation in Learning: Perceptions of Prospective Teachers in a Teacher Education Institution in Northern Pakistan

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Abstract

Motivation plays a pivotal role in the teaching and learning process. It was a qualitative case study to explore prospective teachers' perceptions of the role of motivation in students' learning. The study was carried out in a teacher education institution in a rural setting in Pakistan. The purposive sampling technique was used to select 10 research participants enrolled in a four-year program in education. Semi-structured interviews were used for data collection. All the interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed later for the data analysis. Data were analyzed thematically. The research findings showed that prospective teachers perceive that motivation is a key factor in teaching and learning. They preferred intrinsic motivation and counseling over punishment and rewards. The findings have pertinent implications for teaching and learning as well as for the teacher education programs.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Motivation plays an important role in learning. Learners perform better if they are motivated towards learning. There are several factors that play a role in the motivation of individuals, which include: personal, social, environmental, and cultural. Studies have shown that motivated learners are more likely to undertake challenging tasks, ensure active participation, enjoy their involvement in the activities, take a constructive approach to learning, and exhibit learning in their performance. It is generally seen as a force, stimulus, or influence that triggers a person or organism to act or respond (Dweck et al., 2023). Motivation is a key factor in teaching and learning and creativity. No effective learning will take place without motivation (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Generally, students who are motivated showcase better results. It can affect all aspects of school life, including students' attendance, academic performance, and involvement in learning activities. Therefore, effective teachers constantly motivate students towards learning.

Teachers' behavior and responses can affect learners' motivation. Therefore, it is imperative to explore teachers' perceptions about students' motivation as it plays a vital role in effective teaching and learning. Though there is considerable literature on the perceptions of school teachers about the role of motivation in learning, literature is scarce on how prospective teachers see this phenomenon. This study, therefore, aims to explore the perceptions of prospective teachers about the role of motivation in students' learning and achievements. It is vital to explore how our prospective teachers think about the role of motivation in teaching and learning, as they are the future teachers.

Research Question

What are the perceptions of prospective teachers about the role of motivation in students' learning?

Review of Relevant Literature

Motivation refers to attributes that trigger individuals to do or not to do something (Dweck, Dixon, & Gross, 2023). Motivation is animated by personal enjoyment, interest, or pleasure (Venkatesh, 2011). It energizes individuals for active involvement in activities, prepares them to take challenging tasks, and sustains efforts for further learning and development. Motivation can be depicted in performing tasks, exploration, and taking on challenging tasks. Motivation involves a collection of beliefs, perceptions, values, interests, and actions that are all closely related.

Motivation plays the role of a stepping stone for learning and teaching. It is the desire and interest of individuals to attain goals. Studies have shown that individuals' efforts are proportional to their motivation. To instill motivation among learners, teachers need to take appropriate measures to increase their interest in the topic to be learned through various creative ways, effective planning, and ensuring an appropriate feedback mechanism. Two types of motivation are most referred to, which are called intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The distinction between them has pertinent implications for teaching and learning in educational practices. Intrinsic motivation is internal, and it is the desire to do or achieve something because one truly wants to and takes pleasure or sees value in doing so (Ryan & Deci, 2000). For instance, individuals generally do things for pleasure due to intrinsic motivation. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is the desire to do or achieve something not for the inner pleasure, but because doing so leads to certain results

(Csikszentmihaly, 2014). In other words, extrinsic motivation is a kind of motivation where the purpose is to achieve a result, goal, reward, prize, or complement. Researchers see both types in the form of a spectrum where any action could be motivated by a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Oudeyer et al., 2007).

Intrinsic motivation is due to personal enjoyment, interest, or pleasure. If a learner is doing the work for pleasure and for their enjoyment, then the learner is intrinsically motivated. Intrinsic motivation is also known as an internal drive or push. Alternatively, it is an internal state that drives an individual to act towards achieving certain objectives and goals. Similarly, extrinsic motivation is seen as external motivation or pull. It comes into play when an external goal influences an individual's behavior towards doing something. Therefore, the behavior of an individual is a complex blend of internal pushes and external pulls. From the perspectives of occupation or profession, an individual can be intrinsically motivated to go to work because it makes the individual feel useful and creative. However, at the same time, given the other associated factors and environment, the person just does the work that partly fulfills the person's desires. Intrinsically motivated learners perform activities simply for the enjoyment and satisfaction that comes from completing the activity (Cupita & Andrea, 2016).

Studies have shown that motivation increases the speed of work accomplishment. It also enhances learning performance (Locke & Latham, 2002). It provides energy to creativity, and learners achieve planned tasks and goals given the set directions and commitments to achieve something. Motivated learners can achieve their tasks and objectives easily compared to unmotivated individuals. It is also helpful for teachers in achieving the objectives

of teaching. Motivation influences the teaching and learning process and achievements of curriculum standards and objectives by teachers. It is a fact that motivated teachers play a significant role in the motivation of students (Yenilmez & Çemrek, 2008). For instance, the motivation of a teacher plays a pivotal role in developing the interests of learners in the learning process and developing twenty first century skills that are needed in the current era (Jamil et al., 2025; Jamil & Rizvi, 2025; Naseer et al., 2022).

Studies depict that generally teaching and learning activities involve reward and punishment. Reward refers to making someone excited, willing, and wishful to move towards and achieve goals or accomplish tasks and activities. According to Bandura (1974), when a behavior leads to desirable outcomes, it is more likely to occur in future situations. Likewise, the term punishment is about warning someone to avoid undesirable things, activities, or responses. In other words, it means to penalize or discipline individuals. Thus, punishment is referred to as a process whereby unwanted behavior is followed by negative reinforcement so as to prevent the behavior from reoccurring.

The use of rewards may either encourage or discourage motivation, depending on the type of rewards and the context in which they are given. Since rewards invariably go to a few in class or a group, it is imperative to consider the fate of those who fail and will continue to fail to get a reward. This is likely to affect those who are not able to get the rewards. Similarly, the winners may also face the risk of being victims of jealousy; they may even find themselves ignored or isolated by their peer groups. Therefore, rewards need to be replaced with teaching that is focused on the intrinsic motivation of the learners. Thus, a common goal should be to consider the learners'

interests and make it the center of their learning, not a reward.

Research Design

The study was carried out in a teacher education institution in a rural setting in Pakistan. Qualitative case study method was employed to carry out the study. According to Sukamolson (2007), qualitative research is a type of research that collects non-numerical data and seeks to interpret meaning from collected data that helps us understand the study of the targeted population. A case study is a practical inquiry to explore realities in natural settings based on data generation through various sources. A case study is carried out in a natural situation to get actual information (Easton, 2010).

The purposive sampling technique was used in the study. Such a sampling technique is used for gathering purposeful data from purposefully selected research participants. The researchers selected those research participants who were enrolled in a four-year program in education, and they were in their fifth and sixth semesters. It was felt that after spending four or five semesters, the prospective teachers would have developed an ample repertoire of knowledge about teaching, learning, teaching context, and the learners. Ten participants were selected on a voluntary basis. For this purpose, an information sheet was shared about the study and its possible harms and benefits with the concerned cohort of prospective teachers and allowed them to participate in the study on a truly voluntary basis, and they could quit their participation at any time if they felt so (Khan, Hussain, & Alam, 2021). Semi-structured interviews were used for data collection. The purpose of a semi-structured interview was to find perceptions of prospective teachers about the role of motivation in the learning of students and what they think about the particular. All the

interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed later for the data analysis. The researchers translated the extracts from the transcribed data into English for reporting purposes. Field notes were also maintained during the fieldwork, which further strengthened the process of data generation. The data gathered were analyzed thematically. The researchers received consent from the college administration and from the research participants. Anonymity among the college and research participants was ensured, and they used pseudonyms to hide the actual names of the college and the research participants.

Findings of the Study

Findings of the study have been discussed in detail in the following sections:

Interpretation of Motivation through Analogies

The research participants (prospective teachers) were asked to give analogies or examples from daily life to explain the concept of motivation. As a result, different analogies surfaced from the data analysis explaining the notion of motivation. The most frequently used or most commonly occurring analogies were selected for the analysis. The analogies are given below:

Saira used an analogy of an engine to explain the role of motivation in learning. She said, motivation is like an engine that provides power to a vehicle to run. Without the engine power, a vehicle cannot move. Likewise, without motivation, learning may not happen. Likewise, Haider used the analogy of oxygen for motivation. He saw the importance of motivation for learning as oxygen for life. He said, "Motivation is like oxygen, which is key to the survival of animals. Likewise, motivation plays the role of oxygen for learning. A living being cannot survive without

oxygen; in the same way, learning will not occur without motivation.

Rabia mentioned that motivation is like water for a fish. A fish cannot survive without water. As water is important for a fish, in the same way, motivation is important for learning. In other words, water for fish, motivation for learning!" Thus, she perceived the importance of motivation for learning as that of water for a fish. According to her, teaching and learning are incomplete without motivation.

Iqrar saw motivation as a wing for a bird. He expressed that teaching and learning will never happen in the absence of motivation. He said: Motivation is like a wing for a bird. A bird cannot fly without wings. The more powerful the wings, the higher a bird can fly. Thus, powerful motivation, also known as intrinsic motivation, serves as a wing for a learner, facilitating learning. Motivation from within, or internal, is important.

Jafar, a prospective teacher with a science background, used the analogy of a catalyst in a chemical reaction and explained,

Motivation is like a catalyst used in some chemical reactions. In a chimerical reaction, a catalyst does not take part in the chemical reaction, but speeds it up. For example, manganese dioxide is commonly used as a catalyst in a laboratory to speed up the formation of oxygen. In the same way, motivation plays the role of a catalyst in the learning process. It facilitates learning and speeds it up.

The analogies used by the research participants showcase motivation as a powerful driving force in teaching and learning. The gist of the analogies given above shows that learning needs motivation, and in the absence of motivation, teaching and learning will not happen. Analogies are quite powerful in making sense of individuals' conceptions about certain things. They showcase how individuals see and interpret things. Therefore, the

analogies employed by the prospective teachers showcase their conception of the very notion of motivation and its importance in teaching and learning.

Motivation is a key to success

All the research participants perceived that motivation was a key to success. They believed that motivation is a tool for effective learning and engaging students in various learning activities. Prospective teachers mentioned that through motivation, they can make learners ready for learning. Iqrar expressed, "Without motivation, there will be no engagement in learning activities. As a result, no learning or limited learning will happen. He further mentioned that due to motivation, learners get involved in the process with joy and enthusiasm. Amir shared an anecdote from his B.Ed. A class where a teacher educator had shared a story with them. He explained, "Because of his motivation, a weak student in his class became energetic and eventually became a position holder. Another research participant, Zara, mentioned, "I consider motivation the most important driving factor for learning. Particularly, it is very important for the students in the primary and elementary classes.

Haider proposed, "One cannot deny the importance of motivation in learning. Without motivation, I cannot expect any effective teaching and learning. For me, motivation is the key. A teacher's first responsibility is to engage students in learning through relevant motivation techniques. Haider further explained that during his teaching practicum, he motivated students towards learning through hands-on activities and the use of charts and models. He further explained that he gave responsibilities to various students so as to engage them and motivate them towards learning.

Rabia believed that "no learning would occur without motivation. She further explained that during the practicum, she shared stories from her life and from society; as a result, students became motivated, and they were involved fully in the learning activities. She further mentioned, "A little encouraging comment can become a tool for motivation. Jafar also saw motivation as the most important driving factor in learning. He mentioned that motivation is the key to learning and development. Through motivation, teachers can enhance students' abilities and capabilities to do things. He also explained that due to motivation, learners can change their way of learning and can enjoy their involvement in activities. As a result, they can show better results and achievements.

Salman suggested, "All teachers should realize the importance of motivation in teaching and learning because without motivation, no effective learning will take place. Similarly, according to Kulsoom, "learning solely depends upon motivation because it redirects students' attention towards learning and makes them involved in the learning activities". She further explained, "Motivation plays a pivotal role in making learning effective and joyful". Rabia explained the importance of teacher language in students' motivation. She explained:

Teachers' language plays an important role in motivating students towards learning. Encouraging and constructive comments from teachers always motivate students towards learning. Likewise, discouraging comments from teachers become a hurdle to learning. In some cases, students leave school due to teachers' harsh attitudes.

Rabia further added and mentioned, No one can deny the importance of motivation. Teachers need to have the skills to motivate students. I remember as a child enjoying the classes of the teachers who motivated us towards learning through their language,

gestures, encouraging attitude, and use of a variety of activities in the classes. I still remember those teachers and consider them my role models.

Thus, the research participants believed that motivation was the most important driving force in the teaching and learning process. They believed that they could not expect effective learning without the learners' motivation. Citing examples from their own lives, they also noted that through various activities, teachers can motivate students to learn.

Effectiveness of Intrinsic Motivation

Research participants (Prospective teachers) highlighted types of motivations in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic. However, they preferred the intrinsic motivation to be more powerful and practical than the extrinsic one. To explain the phenomenon, they shared examples from theories they studied in their college program and from their experience in teaching practicum in schools. They believed that intrinsic motivation is internal; therefore, it is more important and powerful. The prospective teachers mentioned that teachers could use different strategies and approaches to motivate students.

Salman, a prospective teacher, mentioned, During the practicum, I experimented with various methods to motivate students to learn. I felt that intrinsic or internal motivation is important. To do this, I used storytelling, shared jokes, and I also noticed that a teacher's body language and gestures can play a key role in motivating students towards learning. Among them, I found storytelling the most powerful in the primary classrooms. I would always share a story to attract students and engage them in learning.

According to Kamal:

I think the learning environment plays a key role in giving intrinsic motivation to students.

It depends on the type of environment teachers create in the classrooms. There should be planned activities for quick learners and slower learners, and all of them should be encouraged. And those who are slow learners and need help with their work completion, teachers should help them by motivating them so that they can do their tasks successfully.

Talking about the role of motivation, Rabia emphasized:

Based on my experience as a student, I realized that a safe, conducive, and encouraging environment plays an important role in students' motivation. If students feel threatened, bullied, mocked or ridiculed, they feel insecure and cannot be motivated to learning. The more secure the students feel, the more they become motivated towards learning. The reason is that in such an environment, students get motivated from within, which is also called internal motivation.

Hussain recorded his thoughts in the following words:

I feel that when students are motivated from the inside, they learn better. Though some people encourage reward and punishment, I do not prefer it. Reward and punishment are external, and they can make students dependent. I feel that intrinsic motivation boosts energy from inside and makes an individual work with passion, and can accept challenging tasks.

To conclude, it has surfaced from the above extracts that the prospective teachers perceive motivation coming from inside as more important, which is also called intrinsic motivation. They also explained the factors that trigger intrinsic motivation among learners. For instance, the highlighted factors include: ensuring a safe and conducive environment; innovative ways of teaching, such as storytelling and use of appropriate teaching resources; scaffolding and encouraging slower learners and providing

advanced learning activities to fast learners; and appropriate use of language by the teachers. The prospective teachers felt that learning based on intrinsic motivation is everlasting, powerful, and flexible. Motivation of this type enables learners to accept challenging tasks and develop a deep-rooted passion for learning.

Counseling Versus Punishment

The research participants rejected the notion of corporal punishment in schools. One of the research participants, Rabia, stressed:

It is a general phenomenon that, through punishment, a teacher can change students' unwanted behavior. But research has neglected this idea. Punishment kills creativity and affects a student's personality badly. Instead of punishment, teachers should be counseling the students, identifying their issues and resolving them.

Another research participant, Kamal, mentioned:

People perceive that punishment is designed to reduce that very behavior in the future. I believe that punishment can work for short-term gains. It can negatively affect the relationship between the punisher and the punished. If the students are punished on a regular basis, they may lose interest in school and drop out. Therefore, teachers should try to find out the reasons behind students' misbehavior and lack of interest, and address them through counseling.

Likewise, Salman observed, "when students are punished frequently, they may believe that they cannot be successful and thus they may quit struggling, lose interest and quit schooling. He further explained that punishment can make learners helpless and make learning impossible for them, and make them aggressive and uncomfortable.

Another participant, Haider, suggested:

There should be no corporal punishment in schools as it has a negative influence on the physical and moral growth of the students. Through punishment, we may control students for a short time, but it will not be effective in the long run. Punishment has no long-term results.

Shafi mentioned, "Because of punishment, students can leave school, and the dropout ratio will increase. He further explained:

In every field of life, there can be some barriers. These barriers can resist learning. Students can face several types of challenges that affect their learning. Teachers can resolve such issues by discussing with the concerned students through counseling. I have seen amazing improvements in students when proper counseling was given to them.

Findings showed that physical punishment has negative effects on the personality of the students and hampers their learning. It has negative implications for students and can affect their physical and moral growth. It surfaced that punishment can increase the dropout ratio in schools. As a result, the research participants suggested using counseling in place of punishment to establish a promising learning environment for both the students and teachers. Counseling not only encourages students to share their problems but also helps them develop empathy with their peers and teachers, which consequently brings about a drastic change in the overall learning environment of the institution.

Discussion of the Findings

Findings in the previous sections show that motivation plays an important role in teaching and learning (Dweck et al., 2023). It was seen as a backbone for effective teaching and learning (Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). In this study, all the research participants perceived that without motivation, there would be no learning and teaching. It surfaced from the

findings that motivation can increase the learning abilities of the students (Dweck, et al., 2023).

Research participants shared different metaphors to explain the very notion of motivation and its role in learning. They saw motivation as "an engine for a vehicle", "Oxygen for life", "water for marine life", "wings for birds", and "catalysts in chemical reactions". All the metaphors used by the research participants showcase the importance of motivation in learning. They show a very powerful message that learning is meaningless, or it may not happen without motivation.

Findings further show that teachers value intrinsic motivation and find it long-lasting, futuristic, overarching, and strengthening the performance of the learners. Researchers like Cerasoli, Nicklin, & Ford (2014) elsewhere in other contexts also found that intrinsic motivation, together with extrinsic motivation, strengthens learning and improves the performance of the learners. Studies on learning have shown that children come from various social and psychological backgrounds and possess diverse learning needs. They are likely to lose motivation when classroom activities do not match their interests and are likely to lose interest as well as feel anxiety in the classroom (Csikszentmihalyi, 2000; Jansen et al., 2022). Therefore, it is imperative for teachers to be aware of the basic psychological needs of the learners and arrange learning activities accordingly (Conesa et al., 2022). Knowing the individual psychological needs of the learners, knowing their aptitudes, and making sense of individual needs will enable teachers to keep learners motivated and engage them in the learning activities.

It surfaced prominently from the findings that students learn most when they are motivated towards learning. The research participants mentioned that learning happens when students are motivated, and motivation

enhances the capabilities of the students, which consequently helps improve learning outcomes. These findings also corroborate with studies carried out by researchers such as Howard et al. (2021). This has some robust implications for teaching and learning. For instance, teachers need to be aware of the instructional designs and pedagogies that are relevant and appropriate to the learners in their classrooms (Jansen et al., 2022).

Findings also show that the research participants preferred counseling to motivate students instead of rewards and punishments. They believe that through counseling, teachers can know more about their students in terms of their interests, aptitudes, behaviors, and learning styles; as a result, teachers can design activities accordingly, as per the interests of the learners. The findings also reinforce the contributions of Renninger & Hidi (2019), who highlighted the importance of interest development and motivation in student learning. Other studies have highlighted that the use of rewards is likely to enhance or hamper motivation, depending on the situation. It is a common phenomenon that rewards generally go to a few in class or a school; therefore, this has implications for those who fail and will continue to fail to get a reward. In other words, this tends to have negative effects on those who fail to get the rewards.

The findings have highlighted the thinking of the prospective teachers about the role of motivation in student learning. Therefore, they have significant implications for policymakers, teacher education institutions, teacher educators, and education service providers.

Conclusion

The study aimed to explore perceptions of prospective teachers about the role of motivation in learning. Findings of the study reveal that motivation is the most important part of learning, and the prospective teachers

perceive that without motivation, there will be no learning. In addition, the prospective teachers see intrinsic motivation as more powerful and encompassing than extrinsic motivation. Findings also show that teachers prefer counselling as compared to punishment. It is due to the reason that counselling provides more room to know about the learners, their individual needs and interests, and design learning activities accordingly.

Recommendations

The following recommendations surfaced by the findings:

Teachers should know about their individual students so as to motivate them towards learning.

School systems and teacher education institutions may arrange training to develop motivation skills among teachers to make their teaching and learning effective.

Teachers should give children confidence and opportunities to explore their hidden abilities and potentials, and share them without any hesitations with their teachers. Schools and teachers should plan classroom activities according to the individual needs of the students, as well as coordinate and educate parents about the aptitudes of their children and subsequent care.

Teacher education programs should enable prospective teachers to understand children's individual needs and prepare them to design teaching and learning activities accordingly.

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